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D2.3 Standard Version 2

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab

Executive summary

Although Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be a “key” to the integration of research and innovation processes in real-life settings, they still fail to provide and function according to unified and harmonized processes that are easily accessible and exploitable by academic and industry researchers. Towards this end, VITALISE aims to create the first Harmonization guidelines for Living Labs that will facilitate the access of researchers to the provided infrastructures.

This document presents the work performed for the Harmonization of the way Living Labs work for the second semester of VITALISE. Taking as a starting point the Standard v0.1, VITALISE performed Harmonization activities with consortium partners and external stakeholders in order to create the Standard v0.2 presented in this document. Standard v0.1 included the state of the art information about Living Labs in the VITALISE consortium and was the first deliverable that set up the structure of the VITALISE Standards. The performed activities for this deliverable included the production and dissemination of a wiki page that included the Standard v0.1 and gives the ability to readers to make comments and suggest adjustments. The Harmonization Board was established and met throughout this second semester. The Harmonization Board consists of experts from the consortium and beyond and is the main Board taking decisions about the Standard Versions. A meeting with the Harmonization Body took place as well, in which participants discussed mainly the Harmonization methodology, the Living Lab management system and the wiki page. The consortium worked also towards updating the parts of the Standard that describe the data and technologies used in living labs, using a Delphi study method and collected the first set of terms for the living lab lexicon.

The final Section of this document presents the Standard v0.2 that will be also published in the living lab harmonization wiki page.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP2

Work Package 2 (WP2), “Common Standards, Procedures and Practices” is a core WP for the VITALISE project as it handles all the work and implementation for the Harmonization procedure that is being followed. Some of the main tasks are the establishment of the harmonization procedures within the consortium and beyond, the management and organization of the Harmonization procedure events (Harmonization Body and Board meetings) and the definition and update of the Standards and Key Performance Indicators by identifying and documenting the existing Living Lab processes, and the similarities and differences among the consortium’s Living Lab partners. The Standard Versions will be updated every six months until the end of VITALISE project.

VITALISE Harmonization Body is a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to co-ordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and consists of representatives from each Living Lab in the consortium, independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document aims to present all the data collection and analysis that has been done between M6-M12 of the VITALISE project regarding the Harmonization activities. Although the deliverable is entitled “Standard Version 2”, the authors of this deliverable decided that the specific standard should be Version 0.2 as it is not yet including all the required parts to reach Version 1.0. This document does not include only the Standard Version 0.2 of the Living Labs services, methods and tools but a more elaborate version, that includes the presentation of data collection and analysis in order to result in the next Standard Version.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of the document.
- **Section 2** discusses the activities that were performed during the second semester of living lab harmonization framework towards the creation of Standard v0.2.
- **Section 3** presents a summary of the changes and new additions that were done in the current version of the standard.
- **Section 4** includes all the information that will constitute the Standard Version 0.2. This Section is a coherent version of the Standard and can be read as a standalone document.
- **Section 5** provides some concluded remarks for this deliverable.

2 Activities performed towards the next standard version

At the beginning of the second iteration for the improvement of Living Lab standard, the Harmonization objective was to redefine and improve the data and technologies taxonomy in line with the requirements collection of the living lab ICT tools, to create the first version of the wiki and engage the community in an open discussion about the standard as well as the establishment of the Harmonization Board in line with VITALISE milestones. This section presents the performed activities towards the realisation of these objectives.

2.1 Establishment of Harmonization Board

The establishment of the Harmonization Board under task 2.2 is part of the Harmonization process in VITALISE. The role of the Harmonization Board is to evaluate and take decisions regarding the Standard Versions of the Living Labs. The Harmonization Board is composed of representatives of Health and Wellbeing Living Labs from the VITALISE consortium as well as external people with expertise and interest in Living Lab and Harmonization procedures.

The selection process for the Harmonization board was the following:

Figure 1: Process establishment Harmonization board

VITALISE' partners suggested names of potential candidates for the Harmonization Board. The potential candidates were contacted by ENoLL and AUTH to verify their interest in joining the VITALISE team. In the second and third week of November 2021, an Open Call was launched in VITALISE channels and ENoLL MailChimp (ANNEX 1) in order to collect applications about externals interested in joining the Harmonization Board of VITALISE.

The open call included information about the expected activities and benefits from joining the Harmonization board. The communication included:

<p>What do I have to do?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Devote some of your time (approx. 3 hours/6 months) and share your knowledge and expertise, to discuss and assess the next Standard of Living Labs Procedures and Services and refine them • Participate in the Harmonization Board General Assembly (in person or remotely, one every 6 months) • Participate in open harmonization events to share valuable knowledge with the community. <p>What's in it for me?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acknowledgement of participation in the Harmonization Board in every version of Living Lab Standard • Participate in joint publications about the Living Labs Harmonization processes • Be a member of a transnational network and explore new opportunities for collaboration • Structure influential material for Living Labs' future in the EU and beyond.

Everyone was invited to apply through a registration form: <https://forms.gle/C65JkWvPZJ3GfFMZA>.

The selection criteria for the Harmonization board relied on two main principles: areas of expertise and level of expertise with Living Labs. Three internal, independent evaluators gave scores to the applicants and the results were notified to the aspirants. Successful applicants also received an NDA document to be signed before joining the VITALISE team. Upon reception of the signed NDA, the first Harmonization Board online meeting took place, and everyone was welcomed to the team.

2.2 Creation of wiki page

VITALISE Project aims to harmonize Living Lab procedures to facilitate and promote open Research & Innovation in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond. To achieve this, a collaborative wiki page to work on the Standard Version for Health and Wellbeing Living Labs was created and published. The aim of the wiki is to guide Living Lab operators and researchers to execute, develop and maintain a harmonized framework for systematic Living Lab practices. We have chosen XWiki as the Living Lab Wiki platform for documentation and collaboration.

XWiki is a free wiki software platform written in Java with a design emphasis on extensibility. It includes WYSIWYG editing, OpenDocument based document import/export, semantic annotations and tagging, and advanced permissions management. XWiki code is licensed under the GNU Lesser General Public License and hosted on GitHub where everyone is free to fork the source code and develop changes in their own repository. The content included in the XWiki wiki is licensed under a Creative Commons attribution license so that it can be redistributed as long as it references XWiki; derivatives can be re-licensed entirely.

As an application wiki, XWiki allows for the storing of structured data and the execution of server-side script within the wiki interface. Scripting languages including Velocity, Apache Groovy, Python, Ruby and PHP can be written directly into wiki pages using wiki macros. User created data structures can be defined in wiki documents and instances of those structures can be attached to wiki documents, stored in a database, and queried using either Hibernate query language or XWiki's own query language. XWiki pages are written by default using the WYSIWYG editor and rendered with XWiki syntax to format text, create tables, create links, display images, etc.

XWiki can be used either as a first generation wiki or a second generation one. First generation wikis are used to collaborate on content. Second generation wikis (a.k.a Structured and Applications Wikis) can be used to create collaborative web applications (by using the wiki paradigm and editing wiki pages).

First generation wiki's basic features:

1. Page editing: Use simple wiki syntax to format text, create tables, create links, display images, etc. Alternatively use a powerful WYSIWYG editor to edit the content of pages.
2. Version Control: Any change made in XWiki is saved under version control, meaning you can view any previous version of a page, compare different versions or rollback to any past version.
3. Rights: Control who can view, edit or delete pages in a flexible manner. Apply rights to a page, its children or an entire wiki.
4. Search: Allows searching on the full wiki using wildcards, faceting search results, getting search result RSS feeds and more.
5. Exports: Export wiki pages to PDF, ODT, RTF, XML or HTML.

Second generation wiki's basic features:

1. Blog: Host one or multiple blogs to communicate information or organise it using categories and tags.
2. File Manager: Manage your folders and files, having viewers for many supported file types (such as office and PDF), displaying a tag cloud and allowing filtering.
3. Meetings: Organise meetings (create, view and modify meetings to come) and send invitations
4. Forums: Discuss important topics using multiple forums that support answers, comments and votes.
5. Tasks: Create and assign tasks for designated projects, with associated assignees and due dates.

2.2.1 Living Lab Harmonization Wiki features

This section presents the Living Lab Harmonization wiki page and the basic functionalities that are offered to the visitor. The VITALISE Living Lab Harmonization Wiki, users are divided into three groups:

1. **Unregistered users**, who will be referred to as **"guests"** for convenience.
2. **Registered users**, who will be referred to as **"users"** for convenience.
3. **Administrators**, who will be referred to as **"admins"** for convenience.

The picture below presents the main screen that is displayed when accessing the Living Lab Harmonization Wiki.

Figure 2: Home screen of Living Lab Harmonization Wiki. For guests, please ignore the numbers 1, 2 and 3.

More specifically:

1. Living Lab Harmonization Wiki, is divided into Pages. Inside the wiki, you can create a hierarchy of pages, by creating pages inside other pages. This feature is called Nested Pages. From this area you can add new pages by clicking the "Create" button (for admins only).
2. Whenever you want to modify a page, click on the "Edit" button, make your changes and save the page (for users). The modified page now replaces the previous version. Each version of the page is stored in the page history and can be reverted to, if needed. More page actions, such as Administer, Copy, Rename, Delete, Export, are also available from the last menu on the right.
3. From the upper right corner, you may click on your profile, or the notifications menu (for users).
4. By expanding the drawer menu on the right, you can log in, register, access your profile or go to the wiki administration (for admins only). You can also access the wiki, page or user index, as well as add a new wiki.
5. You can easily edit/modify the content of the homepage to replace it with your own content.
6. Our menu is handled using panels. A panel is a widget (modified by admins only) you can see on the left and/or right of every page of your wiki in the standard version of XWiki. By default, you will see "Menu" and medium sized panels on the left.

The wiki has an easy-to-use mechanism for managing annotations and comments, offering users and guests an improved experience of interacting with each other.

Figure 3: R&D Services page with annotations on (show mode). For all users.

1. The tabbed area at the bottom of the page features (for all user groups):
 - Comments: You can add comments or interact with other users' comments,
 - Attachments: You will find a collection of the attachments on the current page,
 - Page history: You will find all edits made to this page, major or minor, saved as versions. You have the possibility to compare the versions and revert to a certain one if necessary and
 - Page information: Here you can find page information about locale language, syntax, page reference and other information about page.
2. To annotate a piece of text, select it and hit: Ctrl + M (Meta + M), also you can comment to another user annotation.
 - To show/hide all annotations in the text of the page hit: Alt + A.
 - All annotations also can be found on the comments tab.
3. More page actions, such as Copy, Export, Annotate, Print Preview, Likes, Comments, Attachments, History and Information are also available from the top right corner of the page ("More actions" menu).
4. Before the tabbed area at the bottom of the page, you can "like" a page which also works like "add bookmark" on a browser (for users). Our wiki has tag functionality that allows the grouping of pages under a certain category (only admins can tag pages).

In the edit menu there is a rich editor, with many customization options, which the user can use to edit - modify the page. Only admins have access to direct editing of the pages.

Figure 4: View of the Living Lab Harmonization Wiki home screen in edit mode.

Every user has their own profile page, which they can manage as they wish. They can also easily find and access their latest activity on Wiki. The profile keeps track of all the activities the user does in the wiki page.

Figure 5: Living Lab Harmonization Wiki User Profile page screen, profile tab.

On the profile page, there is the settings menu with the following categories:

- Profile: General user information, that the user can edit (2.). This information is visible to everyone.
- The user can change their password, time zone and more.
- Groups: Which groups the user belongs to.
- Network: The list of users you follow.
- The user can manage their notification setting.
- Pages you liked: A list of pages you liked.

- For admins, we add a Tools page on the menu with admin tools links.

For the proper operation of the Wiki, some tools have been created and added to make the management of the Wiki easier for the administrators.

Figure 6: Living Lab Harmonization Wiki Tools page from the extended admins menu.

- Comments Table: A table with all comments on the wiki.
- Admin Tools: Tools for wiki administration.
- Terminology: A page with Developer shortcuts and edit mode guide.

2.3 Data collection for standard update

Various activities were performed for data collection in order to update the Standard v0.1. Below, these activities, the data collected are presented, as well as the analysis done in order to be able to include them in the Standard version.

2.3.1 Workshops and meetings

Harmonization body meeting

Research objectives and questions: The aim of the workshop was to develop an initial understanding and present the newly established Harmonization methodology and the living lab wiki page.

Sample group: Living Lab researchers and practitioners from the VITALISE consortium and beyond.

Inputs: The wiki page and the Harmonization methodology that is initially presented in D2.1.

Performed activities: During the first Harmonization Body meeting that was carried out on November 30th, 2021, the VITALISE Harmonization methodology was presented and discussed with the Harmonization Body. Then we presented the living lab management system that also governs the Standard version structure. Discussions were carried out about the Business model and the flexibility of the model. Finally, the wiki page was presented, and the participants were asked to try and test it, then make some comments about their experiences.

Harmonization board meeting

Research objectives and questions: The aim of the workshop was to kick-off the activities of the Harmonization Board, create a common understanding among the Team and for the members to get to know each other.

Sample group: The VITALISE Harmonization Board

Inputs: The wiki page and the living lab management system.

Performed activities: During the first Harmonization Board meeting that was carried out on January 20th, 2022 the Harmonization Board introduced themselves to get to know each other. Then, VITALISE team presented the wiki page and the Harmonization methodology and living lab management structure. A discussion followed and the members of the Harmonization Board expressed their view that we should make sure that the Standard Versions do not restrict living lab activities and serendipity but rather be agile and open to changes. The scope of the Standard is to find common ways of working but not impose them.

2.3.2 Comments from the wiki page

During the current iteration of progressively harmonizing procedures and services, the VITALISE Living Labs as well as external researchers, were asked to provide their feedback in the form of comments on the wiki page. The external researchers were invited either by the VITALISE partners directly or through the presentation of the wiki page in various events and meetings (e.g., Harmonization Body Workshop). All the provided feedback and suggestions for improvement were summarized in an excel data base and were categorized based on their content and the section on the wiki page to which they referred. The comments collected concerned both the structure and the organization of the wiki page in order to enhance the coherence and consistency, but also its content, so that it becomes more understandable and comprehensive. Consequently, two independent evaluators reviewed the content of the feedback and resolved any possible conflict and then followed the integration of the provided input into the corresponding parts of the wiki page.

2.3.3 Delphi study towards a taxonomy of data and devices in Living Labs

Living Labs can better integrate the opportunities offered by new ICT concepts and solutions to the specific needs and aspirations of local contexts, cultures, and creativity potentials. Although the use of ICT tools for data collection and digital Health interventions is widely spread among Health and Wellbeing Living Labs, the specific methods and tools used are under researched (Kareborn & Stahlbrost, 2009). There is no available information about ICT and other technical devices used within the Living Lab context in the Health and Wellbeing domain, even though they are frequently used. As a result, there is no systematic understanding what kind of ICT tools and other technical devices are used by living labs and how they can be categorized. The lack of a specific taxonomy creates challenges to external stakeholders that aim to use the services provided by Living Labs as they cannot easily find the tools that they envisage to use. The problem is also extended to data collection since there is no unified representation of the collected datasets, thus impeding the cross-organizational collaboration and the accessibility of Living Labs to external stakeholders.

To this end, VITALISE builds from Standard Version 0.1 a taxonomy for identifying and classifying the data that are collected in Living Lab environments and consequently link the devices that are used for collecting each data category. A method for taxonomy development suggested by Nickerson et al. (2013) (Nickerson et al., 2013) was applied. The taxonomy creation is guided by its intended purpose as different users or different targeted outcomes may lead to different taxonomies (Kwasnik, 1999; Nickerson et al., 2013). To define meta-characteristic, the expected users of the taxonomy were defined as “living lab researchers” and “customers buying/using living lab services”. The aim of the taxonomy is to help finding the appropriate digital data collection tools for living lab research and/or expand understanding about available tools and their possibilities. Furthermore, the taxonomy aims to facilitate data collection by driving a unified representation schema of the collected datasets enabling the the cross-organizational collaboration and the accessibility of Living Labs to external stakeholders. Objective and subjective ending conditions as defined by Nickerson et al. (2013) (Nickerson et al., 2013) were adopted.

The analysis performed in Standard v0.1 about the data collected in Living Labs and the devices that are used in Living Lab research, concluded with 8 categories and 63 subcategories of data that

are gathered from Living Labs using various technologies. This categorization served as a starting point for a Delphi study creation in the 2nd iteration of Living Lab Harmonization process. A definition was formulated by the independent reviewers for each category. The main categories are:

- 1) Activity tracking/monitoring: monitoring and tracking fitness-related metrics such as distance walked or run, calorie consumption, and in some cases heartbeat,
- 2) Assistive technology: used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of persons with disabilities,
- 3) Biometrics: biological measurements — or physical characteristics — that can be used to identify individuals,
- 4) Biosignals: any signal in living beings that can be continually measured and monitored,
- 5) Cognitive function: mental processes within a person's psyche that are present regardless of common circumstances,
- 6) Environment/context monitoring: characterize and monitor the quality of the environment, and establish environmental parameters,
- 7) Physiological monitoring: vital physiologic parameters so that clinicians can be informed of changes in a patient's physiologic condition,
- 8) Virtual reality/interactive technology allowing for a two-way flow of information through an interface between the user and the technology through a simulated experience that can be similar to or completely different from the real world.

2.3.3.1 The Delphi method

The Delphi method is generally agreed that it can extract sound scientific evidence from experts opinions (Fusfeld, 1971) while it is a well-accepted systematic method used when seeking consensus among a panel of experts (Dalkey & Helmer, 1963; Hsu & Sandford, 2007). Moreover, the Delphi study method is commonly used for taxonomy creation (Hanson et al., 2020; Valentijn et al., 2015) as it is widely accepted that such qualitative methods can be appropriate for evaluating design aspect (Iivari & Venable, 2009) including taxonomies. Therefore, the Delphi study method was used as a second step towards the creation of the taxonomy of data and devices In Living Labs.

As per common agreement, the number of survey rounds is guided by the nature of the study and the level of consensus achieved among the participants during each iteration (Akins et al., 2005; Fink-Hafner et al., 2019; Linstone & Turoff, 1975). Our initial planning was to perform iteration rounds posing the same questions until we achieve a supermajority consensus for all the items. This Deliverable reports the first two iterations of the Delphi study. Based on the answers and the complexity of the subject and comments made, the 3rd round will be performed through an online meeting.

2.3.3.2 Recruitment of expert panel

We defined our expert panel based on two criteria:

- professionals that have at least 3 years experience working in health and well being LL and participating in data collection with technical devices
OR
- professionals having experience with ICT tools and data collection in real-life environments

We used purposive and snowball sampling started with a selection of experts within the consortium and the Harmonization Board, aiming to expand to more than the suggested minimum of 20 contributors (Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004) to form an expert panel. We selected 32 experts that demonstrated also heterogeneity in background knowledge and experience as we wanted a diverse sample that would enhance credibility. Our panelists expertise ranged from computer, electronic and technology engineers, medical informatics, psychologists, occupational therapists, organizational and living lab management, clinical and medical expertise. Our panelists were English speakers but coming from 10 different countries (Greece, Canada, Australia, Finland, Spain, Belgium, Hungary,

Austria, Turkey, Netherlands) as we wanted to avoid possible language biases and misinterpretations.

2.3.3.3 Delphi design and online survey

The Delphi was designed and delivered through an online tool¹ that is specially designed for Delphi study delivery. The participants were asked to:

1. Verify the definition of the main categories and provide improvement suggestions.
 2. Make a judgement of which subcategories should belong into which main category
- the definition of the main categories, the participants were asked if they agree or disagree with the definition and whether the definition is easy to understand, on a scale from 1 to 5 (1 as the equivalent for strongly disagree, 4 as the equivalent for strongly agree, and 5 as a negative feedback). Then there was space for comments for each category definition and the possibility to propose the addition of new categories.

Then for each main category, the subcategories were presented, and participants were asked if they agree or disagree with the main category that this subcategory was assigned to and whether the definition is easy to understand, on a scale from 1 to 5 (1 as the equivalent for strongly disagree, 4 as the equivalent for strongly agree, and 5 as a negative feedback). Then there was again space for comments for each subcategory and the possibility to propose the addition of new items in that main category.

2.3.3.4 Delphi consensus process and synthesis of the results

The consensus for the Delphi study was set based on the criteria defined in the VITALISE Harmonization methodology (more information on D2.1 and D2.2). Based on that an item is considered accepted if it reaches strong supermajority threshold of 80% consensus. For each item the percentage of positive (3 and 4) and negative responses (1 and 2) was calculated. If that percentage exceeded the threshold of 80%, the item was maintained in the taxonomy. If not, two independent evaluators analysed the qualitative information aiming to find the agreement points, based on the following criteria:

1. The comments were reviewed taking into account the number of panelists presenting similar comments. We acted on comments made by one individual in exception, as these were considered outlying discrepant viewpoints from the consensus.
2. Every independent reviewer made suggestions based on the qualitative comments and literature in the area.
3. Changes in the items that have achieved supermajority consensus could be proposed if the understanding of the item remains low and the qualitative comments or literature information can sufficiently justify it.
4. A consensus meeting followed in order to determine the version for the next round. We agreed changes to items provided we could sufficiently justify them based on qualitative comments and author group consensus.

2.3.3.5 Results

From the 32 invited participants, we received 18 responses (56,25% response rate) in round 1. We only invited respondents of round 1 to complete round 2. All the 18 participants responded in round 2 (100% response rate)

¹ www.edelphi.org

2.3.3.5.1 ROUND 1

Below we present the results of the 1st Round of eDelphi quantitative results.

Table 1: Agreement with main categories definition

Agreement with main categories definition						
	Disagree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1 Activity tracking/monitoring	22%	78%	0%	22%	39%	39%
2 Assistive technology	12%	88%	0%	12%	35%	53%
3 Biometrics	6%	94%	0%	6%	38%	56%
4 Biosignals	25%	75%	0%	25%	38%	38%
5 Cognitive function	29%	71%	6%	24%	47%	24%
6 Environment/context monitoring	29%	71%	0%	29%	41%	29%
7 Physiological monitoring	22%	78%	6%	17%	56%	22%
8 Virtual reality/interactive technology	6%	94%	0%	6%	56%	39%

Table 2: Agreement with how easy it is to understand description

Easiness to understand main categories						
	Disagree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1 Activity tracking/monitoring	17%	83%	0%	17%	50%	33%
2 Assistive technology	0%	100%	0%	0%	35%	65%
3 Biometrics	13%	88%	0%	13%	31%	56%
4 Biosignals	33%	67%	0%	33%	39%	28%
5 Cognitive function	44%	56%	11%	33%	17%	39%
6 Environment/context monitoring	29%	71%	0%	29%	35%	35%
7 Physiological monitoring	11%	89%	6%	6%	56%	33%
8 Virtual reality/interactive technology	6%	94%	0%	6%	50%	44%

As we can see only 3 of the categories achieved a supermajority consensus on both agreement and clear description of the category. Furthermore, from the qualitative comments came out that there was not clearly defined if the categories were aimed at classifying data collection devices or technologies for intervention. For this reason, a higher distinction level was created dividing the categories to “Categories of devices for data monitoring and collection” and “Categories of technologies for interventions”. The “Categories of devices for data monitoring and collection” were also divided into Environmental and Human monitoring.

As there was a major misunderstanding between biosignals and physiological monitoring and the differences among them were not clearly defined, a new category replaced the initial ones called “Biosignals and Physiological monitoring”. Furthermore, based on the suggestion by two panel members and with the support of the literature a new category was included, the “vital signs” based on the HL7 framework classification. The category of “Mobile and Computer games” was added as well.

Table 3: The new categories and definitions are presented below:

			New Definition
Categories of devices for data monitoring and collection		Environmental monitoring	characterize and monitor the environment, establish environmental parameters and conditions. As environment we refer to the person's surroundings either indoors or outdoors.
	Human monitoring	Biometrics	biological measurements — or physical characteristics — that can be used to identify individuals and their unique characteristics such as fingerprint scanning or voice recognition
		Biosignals and physiological monitoring	physiological and physical measures of the human body's functions, in individuals. This can occur in a resting condition or in response to certain bodily or environmental conditions. It includes also fitness related metrics
		(Primary) Vital signs	a group of the six most important medical signs that indicate the status of the body's vital function (diastolic/systolic blood pressure, body temperature, heart rate, respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, body height, body weight, BMI, head circumference)
		Cognitive ability and mental processes	Measuring the processes involved in the acquisition of knowledge, reasoning and management of information and the brain-based skills we need to carry out any task
		Activity and behavioral monitoring	monitoring the individuals' physical activities and tracking their performance. Monitoring behavior and activities of daily living (ADLs)
Categories of technologies for interventions		Assistive Technology	technologies used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of individuals, the feeling of autonomy, safety and general wellbeing or also supporting participation.
		Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)	allows for a two-way flow of information through an interface between the user and the technology through a simulated experience that can be similar to or completely different from the real world

		Mobile and Computer Games	all the digital games that are used as interventions for health and wellbeing not including XR
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The following tables present the agreement and easiness to understand for specific items in each main category. The first column presents the main category while the second includes the subcategory.

Table 4: Agreement in the item belonging to a main category

Agreement with items belonging in the main category							
	Item name	Disagree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. ACT	1. Blood oxygen	40%	60%	13%	27%	33%	27%
2. ACT	2. Blood sugar level	33%	67%	7%	27%	33%	33%
3. ACT	3. Body battery	75%	25%	33%	42%	17%	8%
4. ACT	4. Body position	13%	87%	0%	13%	40%	47%
5. ACT	5. Calories burned	29%	71%	14%	14%	36%	36%
6. ACT	6. Energy expenditure	38%	63%	25%	13%	31%	31%
7. ACT	7. Gait	21%	79%	0%	21%	36%	43%
8. ACT	8. Human balance	25%	75%	6%	19%	31%	44%
9. ACT	9. Inverse kinematics data	14%	86%	0%	14%	57%	29%
10. ACT	10. Movement measurement	6%	94%	0%	6%	44%	50%
11. ACT	11. Orientation	29%	71%	0%	29%	36%	36%
12. ACT	12. Physical activity	19%	81%	0%	19%	38%	44%
13. ACT	13. Physical performance	21%	79%	0%	21%	36%	43%
14. ACT	14. Physiological and behavioural biomarkers	31%	69%	6%	25%	25%	44%
15. ACT	15. Sleep	21%	79%	0%	21%	36%	43%
16. ACT	16. Steps	6%	94%	0%	6%	38%	56%
17. ACT	17. Stress level	36%	64%	0%	36%	43%	21%
18. ACT	18. Temperature	43%	57%	7%	36%	43%	14%
19. ACT	19. Vo2	36%	64%	0%	36%	29%	36%
20. ACT	20. Well-being evaluation	38%	63%	19%	19%	38%	25%
1. ASS	1. Alarm system	46%	54%	0%	46%	23%	31%
2. ASS	2. Engaged users	50%	50%	21%	29%	21%	29%
3. ASS	3. Natural language understanding	8%	92%	0%	8%	50%	42%
4. ASS	4. Safe bathroom usage	8%	92%	8%	0%	46%	46%
5. ASS	5. Safe walk assistance	9%	91%	0%	9%	36%	55%
6. ASS	6. Technology Usage habits	23%	77%	8%	15%	46%	31%
7. ASS	7. Video stream	55%	45%	27%	27%	36%	9%
8. ASS	8. Voice commands	21%	79%	14%	7%	64%	14%
9. ASS	9. Walking speed	46%	54%	15%	31%	31%	23%
1. BIOM	1. Basic Biometrics	7%	93%	7%	0%	43%	50%
1. BIOSIG	1. ECG	0%	100%	0%	0%	40%	60%
2. BIOSIG	2. EEG	0%	100%	0%	0%	44%	56%
3. BIOSIG	3. Electrophysiological timeseries	14%	86%	7%	7%	43%	43%
4. BIOSIG	4. Heart rate	6%	94%	0%	6%	31%	63%
1. COGNI	1. Cognitive training	64%	36%	14%	50%	21%	14%
1. ENVMON	1. Alarm system	21%	79%	14%	7%	29%	50%

2. ENVMON	2. Blind operation	40%	60%	30%	10%	30%	30%
3. ENVMON	3. Concentration levels	23%	77%	8%	15%	46%	31%
4. ENVMON	4. Door operation	33%	67%	17%	17%	33%	33%
5. ENVMON	5. Indoor movements	14%	86%	0%	14%	43%	43%
6. ENVMON	6. Luminosity	0%	100%	0%	0%	42%	58%
7. ENVMON	7. Technical alerts (Flood)	8%	92%	0%	8%	46%	46%
8. ENVMON	8. Technical alerts (Smoke)	11%	89%	0%	11%	44%	44%
9. ENVMON	9. Technical alerts (Temperature)	21%	79%	21%	0%	50%	29%
1. PHYMON	1. Patient history & demographics	21%	79%	0%	21%	43%	36%
2. PHYMON	2. Virtual reality	38%	62%	8%	31%	38%	23%
3. PHYMON	3. Weight BMI	7%	93%	7%	0%	60%	33%
1. VR	1. Alternative and augmentative Interaction	13%	88%	6%	6%	63%	25%
2. VR	2. Gesture detection (smile)	29%	71%	0%	29%	57%	14%
3. VR	3. Intuitive user interface	25%	75%	13%	13%	50%	25%
4. VR	4. Web Interaction	31%	69%	0%	31%	46%	23%

Table 5: Agreement is the item description "easy to understand"

Agreement with easiness to understand subcategories							
Item name		Disagree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. ACT	1. Blood oxygen	6%	94%	6%	0%	56%	38%
2. ACT	2. Blood sugar level	27%	73%	7%	20%	33%	40%
3. ACT	3. Body battery	20%	80%	0%	20%	47%	33%
4. ACT	4. Body position	33%	67%	0%	33%	33%	33%
5. ACT	5. Calories burned	0%	100%	0%	0%	33%	67%
6. ACT	6. Energy expenditure	40%	60%	13%	27%	27%	33%
7. ACT	7. Gait	13%	88%	0%	13%	38%	50%
8. ACT	8. Human balance	15%	85%	0%	15%	38%	46%
9. ACT	9. Inverse kinematics data	54%	46%	31%	23%	31%	15%
10. ACT	10. Movement measurement	20%	80%	0%	20%	33%	47%
11. ACT	11. Orientation	27%	73%	7%	20%	33%	40%
12. ACT	12. Physical activity	13%	87%	0%	13%	27%	60%
13. ACT	13. Physical performance	20%	80%	0%	20%	40%	40%
14. ACT	14. Physiological and behavioural biomarkers	21%	79%	0%	21%	64%	14%
15. ACT	15. Sleep	20%	80%	7%	13%	53%	27%
16. ACT	16. Steps	7%	93%	0%	7%	21%	71%
17. ACT	17. Stress level	7%	93%	0%	7%	47%	47%
18. ACT	18. Temperature	7%	93%	0%	7%	50%	43%
19. ACT	19. Vo2	31%	69%	8%	23%	38%	31%
20. ACT	20. Well-being evaluation	7%	93%	7%	0%	64%	29%
1. ASS	1. Alarm system	13%	87%	0%	13%	40%	47%
2. ASS	2. Engaged users	25%	75%	8%	17%	33%	42%

3. ASS	3. Natural language understanding	29%	71%	7%	21%	43%	29%
4. ASS	4. Safe bathroom usage	50%	50%	10%	40%	30%	20%
5. ASS	5. Safe walk assistance	33%	67%	8%	25%	42%	25%
6. ASS	6. Technology Usage habits	29%	71%	7%	21%	43%	29%
7. ASS	7. Video stream	21%	79%	7%	14%	50%	29%
8. ASS	8. Voice commands	0%	100%	0%	0%	64%	36%
9. ASS	9. Walking speed	27%	73%	0%	27%	33%	40%
1. BIOM	1. Basic Biometrics	29%	71%	14%	14%	36%	36%
1. BIOSIG	1. ECG	13%	88%	6%	6%	44%	44%
2. BIOSIG	2. EEG	0%	100%	0%	0%	31%	69%
3. BIOSIG	3. Electrophysiological timeseries	14%	86%	7%	7%	36%	50%
4. BIOSIG	4. Heart rate	0%	100%	0%	0%	31%	69%
1. COGNI	1. Cognitive training	29%	71%	7%	21%	36%	36%
1. ENVMON	1. Alarm system	0%	100%	0%	0%	58%	42%
2. ENVMON	2. Blind operation	27%	73%	9%	18%	36%	36%
3. ENVMON	3. Concentration levels	46%	54%	23%	23%	38%	15%
4. ENVMON	4. Door operation	21%	79%	14%	7%	57%	21%
5. ENVMON	5. Indoor movements	57%	43%	29%	29%	36%	7%
6. ENVMON	6. Luminosity	31%	69%	8%	23%	54%	15%
7. ENVMON	7. Technical alerts (Flood)	23%	77%	8%	15%	31%	46%
8. ENVMON	8. Technical alerts (Smoke)	7%	93%	0%	7%	43%	50%
9. ENVMON	9. Technical alerts (Temperature)	8%	92%	0%	8%	50%	42%
1. PHYMON	1. Patient history & demographics	31%	69%	8%	23%	46%	23%
2. PHYMON	2. Virtual reality	22%	78%	0%	22%	22%	56%
3. PHYMON	3. Weight BMI	21%	79%	0%	21%	50%	29%
1. VR	1. Alternative and augmentative Interaction	33%	67%	8%	25%	33%	33%
2. VR	2. Gesture detection (smile)	42%	58%	8%	33%	33%	25%
3. VR	3. Intuitive user interface	18%	82%	0%	18%	36%	45%
4. VR	4. Web Interaction	31%	69%	8%	23%	31%	38%

As presented in the previous tables, there was a major disagreement and misunderstanding of the subcategories. Based on the qualitative results and the new categories that were created, the reviewers of the Delphi came up with the following new subcategories.

Table 6: New categories and subcategories.

Category	Subcategory
Environment monitoring	Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)
	Technical alerts (Flood)
	Technical alerts (Smoke)
	Environmental Temperature (air or water temperature)
	Luminosity
	Indoor movements
Biometrics	Face recognition
	Voice recognition
Biosignals and physiological monitoring (excluding vital signs)	Physiological and behavioural biomarkers
	Electrophysiological timeseries
	EEG
	ECG
	EMG (electromyography)
	GSR (galvanic skin response)
	Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)
	Blood oxygen
	Blood sugar level
(Primary) Vital signs	Diastolic blood pressure
	Systolic blood pressure
	Heart rate
	Body temperature
	Respiratory rate
	Oxygen saturation
	Body height
	Body length
	Body weight
	Body Mass Index
Cognitive ability and mental processes	Questionnaires of cognitive function
	Cognitive tasks and paradigms
	Memory
	Attention
Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	Body position
	Orientation

	Walking speed
	Gait
	Human balance
	Inverse kinematics data
	Movement measurement
	Physical activity
	Physical performance
	Sleep
	Steps
	Stress level
	Physical performance
	Digital questionnaires and surveys
	Video stream
	Fall detection
	Gesture detection
	Audio stream
Assistive Technology	Cognitive training
	Supporting bathroom usage
	Walk assistance
	Mobile apps
	Alarm system
	Natural language understanding
Virtual reality/interactive technology	Alternative and augmentative Interaction
	Intuitive user interface
Mobile and Computer Games	Mobile games
	Computer games

2.3.3.5.2 ROUND 2

Round 1 had introduced a higher-level categorization that was verified in Round 2. The panelists were asked to declare if they agree on the inclusion of each category in the “data monitoring and collection” and “intervention” technologies and if this distinction is useful, easy to understand and necessary. As presented in the following table supermajority was reached for all the categories, so the higher-level categorization was adopted.

Table 7: New higher level categorization.

Agreement with higher level categorization							
Type	Variable	Disagree	Agree	1	2	3	4
Useful	Data monitoring VS intervention technologies	0%	100%	0%	0%	38%	62%
Easy	Data monitoring VS intervention technologies	7%	93%	0%	7%	60%	33%
Necessary	Data monitoring VS intervention technologies	0%	100%	0%	0%	69%	31%
Useful	Environmental monitoring VS human monitoring	0%	100%	0%	0%	77%	23%
Easy	Environmental monitoring VS human monitoring	13%	87%	0%	13%	67%	20%
Necessary	Environmental monitoring VS human monitoring	0%	100%	0%	0%	58%	42%
Belong	Biometrics to Human monitoring	7%	93%	0%	7%	60%	33%
Belong	Biosignals to Human monitoring	7%	93%	0%	7%	29%	64%
Belong	Vital signs to Human monitoring	0%	100%	0%	0%	40%	60%
Belong	Cognitive ability to Human monitoring	0%	100%	0%	0%	33%	67%
Belong	Activity monitoring to Human monitoring	7%	93%	0%	7%	33%	60%
Belong	Assistive Technology to intervention	0%	100%	0%	0%	33%	67%
Belong	Extended reality to interventions	0%	100%	0%	0%	31%	69%
Belong	Games to interventions	0%	100%	0%	0%	31%	69%

The agreement on the general categories is also presented below

Table 8: Agreement in the item belonging to a main category

Agreement with item belonging in main categories							
Group	Long name	Disagree	Agree	1	2	3	4
ACTMON	Walking speed	7%	93%	0%	7%	47%	47%
ACTMON	Orientation	0%	100%	0%	0%	55%	45%
ACTMON	Body position	7%	93%	0%	7%	57%	36%
ACTMON	Gait	8%	92%	0%	8%	38%	54%
ACTMON	Human balance	7%	93%	0%	7%	43%	50%
ACTMON	Inverse kinematics data	10%	90%	0%	10%	40%	50%
ACTMON	Movement measurement	13%	87%	0%	13%	47%	40%
ACTMON	Physical activity	7%	93%	0%	7%	40%	53%
ACTMON	Physical performance	0%	100%	0%	0%	71%	29%
ACTMON	Sleep	7%	93%	0%	7%	47%	47%
ACTMON	Steps	0%	100%	0%	0%	60%	40%

ACTMON	Stress level	21%	79%	7%	14%	36%	43%
ACTMON	Technology usage patterns	17%	83%	0%	17%	67%	17%
ACTMON	Video stream	40%	60%	0%	40%	50%	10%
ACTMON	Fall detection	0%	100%	0%	0%	62%	38%
ACTMON	Gesture detection	27%	73%	9%	18%	36%	36%
ACTMON	Digital questionnaires and surveys	50%	50%	30%	20%	20%	30%
ACTMON	Audio stream	40%	60%	0%	40%	40%	20%
ASSTECH	Cognitive training	0%	100%	0%	0%	64%	36%
ASSTECH	Supporting bathroom usage	0%	100%	0%	0%	58%	42%
ASSTECH	Mobile apps	23%	77%	15%	8%	46%	31%
ASSTECH	Alarm system	7%	93%	0%	7%	47%	47%
ASSTECH	Natural language understanding	14%	86%	0%	14%	43%	43%
ASSTECH	Walk assistance	0%	100%	0%	0%	47%	53%
BIOM	Face recognition	7%	93%	7%	0%	29%	64%
BIOM	Voice recognition	8%	92%	8%	0%	31%	62%
BIOSIG	Physiological and behavioural biomarkers	0%	100%	0%	0%	36%	64%
BIOSIG	Electrophysiological timeseries	0%	100%	0%	0%	40%	60%
BIOSIG	EEG (electroencephalography)	0%	100%	0%	0%	31%	69%
BIOSIG	ECG (electrocardiography)	0%	100%	0%	0%	31%	69%
BIOSIG	EMG (electromyography)	0%	100%	0%	0%	31%	69%
BIOSIG	GSR (galvanic skin response)	0%	100%	0%	0%	42%	58%
BIOSIG	Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)	7%	93%	0%	7%	36%	57%
BIOSIG	Blood oxygen	0%	100%	0%	0%	43%	57%
BIOSIG	Blood sugar level	0%	100%	0%	0%	36%	64%
COGNI	Questionnaires of cognitive function	8%	92%	0%	8%	33%	58%
COGNI	Cognitive tasks and paradigms	8%	92%	0%	8%	25%	67%
COGNI	Memory	8%	92%	0%	8%	38%	54%
COGNI	Attention	8%	92%	0%	8%	38%	54%
ENVMON	Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)	0%	100%	0%	0%	33%	67%
ENVMON	Technical alerts (Flood)	13%	87%	0%	13%	60%	27%
ENVMON	Technical alerts (Smoke)	7%	93%	0%	7%	53%	40%
ENVMON	Environmental temperature (air temperature)	0%	100%	0%	0%	50%	50%
ENVMON	Environmental temperature (water temperature)	7%	93%	0%	7%	53%	40%
ENVMON	Luminosity	0%	100%	0%	0%	67%	33%
ENVMON	Indoor movements	23%	77%	8%	15%	38%	38%
GAMES	Mobile games	8%	92%	8%	0%	58%	33%
GAMES	Computer games	8%	92%	8%	0%	67%	25%
VITALS	Diastolic blood pressure	0%	100%	0%	0%	50%	50%
VITALS	Systolic blood pressure	0%	100%	0%	0%	50%	50%
VITALS	Heart rate	0%	100%	0%	0%	47%	53%
VITALS	Body temperature	7%	93%	0%	7%	53%	40%
VITALS	Respiratory rate	0%	100%	0%	0%	53%	47%
VITALS	Oxygen saturation	0%	100%	0%	0%	57%	43%

VITALS	Body height	57%	43%	29%	29%	14%	29%
VITALS	Body length	69%	31%	38%	31%	15%	15%
VITALS	Body weight	50%	50%	21%	29%	21%	29%
VITALS	Body Mass Index	53%	47%	27%	27%	27%	20%
XR	Alternative and augmentative Interaction	0%	100%	0%	0%	40%	60%
XR	Intuitive user interface	40%	60%	20%	20%	30%	30%

Table 9: Agreement in the item description "easy to understand"

Easiness to understand items in main categories							
Group	Long name	Disagree	Agree	1	2	3	4
ACTMON	Activity and behavioral monitoring	21%	79%	0%	21%	43%	36%
ACTMON	Walking speed	0%	100%	0%	0%	40%	60%
ACTMON	Orientation	29%	71%	7%	21%	43%	29%
ACTMON	Body position	21%	79%	0%	21%	57%	21%
ACTMON	Gait	21%	79%	7%	14%	57%	21%
ACTMON	Human balance	20%	80%	7%	13%	53%	27%
ACTMON	Inverse kinematics data	40%	60%	20%	20%	40%	20%
ACTMON	Movement measurement	21%	79%	0%	21%	50%	29%
ACTMON	Physical activity	7%	93%	0%	7%	67%	27%
ACTMON	Physical performance	29%	71%	0%	29%	57%	14%
ACTMON	Sleep	13%	87%	0%	13%	47%	40%
ACTMON	Steps	0%	100%	0%	0%	40%	60%
ACTMON	Stress level	14%	86%	0%	14%	43%	43%
ACTMON	Technology usage patterns	29%	71%	7%	21%	57%	14%
ACTMON	Video stream	58%	42%	17%	42%	33%	8%
ACTMON	Fall detection	14%	86%	0%	14%	50%	36%
ACTMON	Gesture detection	21%	79%	0%	21%	50%	29%
ACTMON	Digital questionnaires and surveys	31%	69%	8%	23%	38%	31%
ACTMON	Audio stream	58%	42%	0%	58%	33%	8%
ASSTECH	Assistive Technology	14%	86%	7%	7%	29%	57%
ASSTECH	Cognitive training	7%	93%	0%	7%	67%	27%
ASSTECH	Supporting bathroom usage	7%	93%	0%	7%	57%	36%
ASSTECH	Mobile apps	27%	73%	13%	13%	53%	20%
ASSTECH	Alarm system	7%	93%	0%	7%	53%	40%
ASSTECH	Natural language understanding	20%	80%	0%	20%	53%	27%
ASSTECH	Walk assistance	0%	100%	0%	0%	67%	33%
BIOM	Face recognition	0%	100%	0%	0%	43%	57%
BIOM	Voice recognition	0%	100%	0%	0%	46%	54%
BIOMON	Biometrics	0%	100%	0%	0%	20%	80%
BIOSIG	Biosignals and physiological monitoring	33%	67%	0%	33%	27%	40%
BIOSIG	Physiological and behavioural biomarkers	36%	64%	7%	29%	50%	14%
BIOSIG	Electrophysiological timeseries	29%	71%	7%	21%	50%	21%
BIOSIG	EEG (electroencephalography)	7%	93%	7%	0%	36%	57%
BIOSIG	ECG (electrocardiography)	7%	93%	0%	7%	40%	53%

BIOSIG	EMG (electromyography)	14%	86%	7%	7%	36%	50%
BIOSIG	GSR (galvanic skin response)	14%	86%	7%	7%	50%	36%
BIOSIG	Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)	21%	79%	0%	21%	29%	50%
BIOSIG	Blood oxygen	0%	100%	0%	0%	60%	40%
BIOSIG	Blood sugar level	0%	100%	0%	0%	47%	53%
COGNI	Questionnaires of cognitive function	21%	79%	0%	21%	57%	21%
COGNI	Cognitive tasks and paradigms	36%	64%	0%	36%	43%	21%
COGNI	Memory	20%	80%	0%	20%	47%	33%
COGNI	Attention	27%	73%	0%	27%	53%	20%
CONGNI	Cognitive ability and mental processes	21%	79%	0%	21%	50%	29%
ENVMON	Environmental monitoring Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)	13%	87%	0%	13%	33%	53%
ENVMON	Technical alerts (Flood)	7%	93%	0%	7%	60%	33%
ENVMON	Technical alerts (Smoke)	27%	73%	0%	27%	53%	20%
ENVMON	Environmental temperature (air temperature)	27%	73%	0%	27%	47%	27%
ENVMON	Environmental temperature (water temperature)	7%	93%	0%	7%	57%	36%
ENVMON	Luminosity	20%	80%	0%	20%	47%	33%
ENVMON	Indoor movements	23%	77%	15%	8%	54%	23%
GAMES	Mobile and Computer Games	15%	85%	0%	15%	54%	31%
GAMES	Mobile games	13%	87%	0%	13%	47%	40%
GAMES	Computer games	38%	62%	8%	31%	31%	31%
VITALS	Vital signs	42%	58%	8%	33%	42%	17%
VITALS	Diastolic blood pressure	7%	93%	0%	7%	40%	53%
VITALS	Systolic blood pressure	7%	93%	0%	7%	43%	50%
VITALS	Heart rate	7%	93%	0%	7%	47%	47%
VITALS	Body temperature	0%	100%	0%	0%	40%	60%
VITALS	Respiratory rate	0%	100%	0%	0%	53%	47%
VITALS	Oxygen saturation	0%	100%	0%	0%	67%	33%
VITALS	Body height	0%	100%	0%	0%	57%	43%
VITALS	Body length	27%	73%	13%	13%	33%	40%
VITALS	Body weight	47%	53%	20%	27%	27%	27%
VITALS	Body Mass Index	27%	73%	13%	13%	33%	40%
XR	Extended reality Alternative and augmentative	27%	73%	13%	13%	40%	33%
XR	Interaction	21%	79%	0%	21%	36%	43%
XR	Intuitive user interface	31%	69%	8%	23%	38%	31%

2.3.4 Collection of lexicon terms

VITALISE is creating a Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) with the aim of facilitating the use of terminology from Living Labs in the Health and Well-being sector. The LLL will be grounded on a Wikipedia type of user interface and will cover categories such as Strategy, governance & culture; Operations & infrastructure; Openness; Users & reality; Impact & value creation, and Stability of the living lab. The creation process for the first collection of terms for the Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) was:

Figure 7: Creation process of the Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)

The Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) team defined the aim of the Lexicon and followed with the selection of categories to be included in the LLL. Based on the KPI developed in WP2 and in OpenLab H2020 project. The categories selected intended to be only a point of reference to collect more terms from Living Labs’ activities. The team decided not to limit the terminology to these categories exclusively.

The following step was to disseminate an Open form for collecting the terms, to the Living Labs’ ecosystem from the VITALISE consortium and ENoLL. The form was designed to collect “terms used in living lab activities” in an anonymous way.

The participants were able to get some inspiration from a cloud of terms used in Living Labs and were asked to provide input from their experience working with Living Labs. The results pointed to a new word cloud with 33 words.

Table 10: Collected terms from LLs' activities

Collected terms from LLs' activities			
bottom up	european collaboration	integrative process	observation
co-design	experimentation	iterative feedback	open innovation ecosystem
community pilots	exploration	knowledge sharing	real life testing
constellation	feedback protection	lifecycle approach	regional collaboration
cross border living lab collaboration	governance	living lab methodology	small scale pilots
Cross-fertilization	human centered design	living lab methods and tools	stakeholders
demonstration (sessions)	human factor study	living lab research	user centered-design
end user involvement uptake inclusion	ideation	methodology	user design research
end users			

The gathering of terms is still ongoing and after the first collection of words, the VITALISE team will work with a linguist and psycholinguist expert (from the consortium) to reshape the structure and creation of the Living Lab Lexicon (LLL).

3 Updates on the Standard

3.1 Overview of updates

Based on the VITALISE Harmonization methodology (more information can be found on D2.2), at the beginning of each standard iteration we define the objectives of the current that also needs to be in line with the ongoing activities in the project. Based on the objectives we can afterwards define which activities will be performed to realize each objective. For this Deliverable, the objectives that were defined along with the related project activities are presented in the following table.

Table 11: Objectives with the related project activities presentation.

Standard and delivery date	Objective	Related project activities
Standard Version 2 – March 2022 [M12]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and devices updated version • First version of lexicon (collection of terms) • Updated wiki page structure • Living Lab Business Model updates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of user requirements (data and devices related) • Refinement of JRAs protocols • First open call for external researchers

Overall, the conceptual overview of the Living Lab management system remained the same. Some Section that were not described in Standard Version 0.1 are included in that deliverable while some of the rest are updated. An overview of the changes for the different sections is presented below.

The following sections present the parts that were updated in Living Lab Standard for v0.1 to v0.2. The numbering of the parts is not consecutive as not all the parts are updated.

3.2 PART 1. Lexicon

The need for a Lexicon appeared multiple times in VITALISE communications and workshops with the Harmonization Body and Board but also in communications with ENoLL members. As described in Section 2.3.4, in this version we aim to collect a first set of terms based on the input from the Living Lab community.

3.3 PART 2. Living Lab Business Model (LLBM)

The Living Lab Business Model Part consists of various sections, grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC). In this version we re-define and improve the customer segments part. There were several comments in the wiki page about the customers sections which was considered more oriented on businesses, healthcare organizations, public authorities and universities and not about the researchers. There were proposals about classifying professionals involved in research and direct customers as researchers might not be the ones who pay for Living Lab services directly. In addition, it was proposed that the end users (consumers) of the project's results are included, because without it the successful innovation phase of the project cannot be imagined. A significant part of the users provides feedback on the experience of using the results of the project, and will even create new ideas and suggestions, which will form the basis for further innovation.

Towards this end and taking into account the comments made, the customer section was redesigned in order to include end-users and living lab infrastructure end-users. For identifying the non-professional end users (a.k.a. study participants) we analysed and categorized the information provided by each living lab for the open call application material².

² <https://vitalise-project.eu/living-labs/>

3.4 PART 5. R&D Services

The input for the R&D Services mainly came from the comments in the wiki page. One main addition was the identification of the descriptive information items that are used for each services. Also, there were various comments about the categorization of R&D services as it may be more clear for the reader to organize the list of R&D services by grouping them and also ranking them according to the flow of a living lab process to avoid a list of terminologies that are a lot to digest. As there were some conflicting suggestions the Harmonization team decided that this will be clarified by the Harmonization Body in a meeting.

3.5 PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure

A first attempt for defining the living lab research infrastructure categories is also included in the Standard version. The categorization is grounded on the RI typology proposed by Horizon 2020 funded RI-PATHS-project (No 777563).

3.6 PART 7B. Devices and technologies

The devices and technologies taxonomy was updated based on the outcomes of the Delphi study. The outcomes of Round 2 are included in the current standard version as they are the ones that have been verified by the panelists. A consensus meeting will follow in Round 3 that will be reported in a later standard version of the living lab standard.

4 Standard Version 0.2

This Section will be the second (v0.2) public version of Living Labs Standard. This Standard is considered Version 0.2 as there are still sections that are not defined and have not undergone a full cycle of Harmonization. As v1.0 we are considering the first version that will contain information for all available sections. This Section is structured in such a way so that it can be separated from the rest of the deliverable and published in the VITALISE wiki page as a standalone document.

4.1 Introduction

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) – an international non-profit association promoting and enhancing user-driven innovation ecosystem defines living lab as *“a user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings”* (<https://enoll.org/about-us/>).

This wiki serves as an open space for the public review of the harmonization version and encourages open discussion about the various items that are presented. The information presented in this wiki will be updated every six months and published after approval from the governance Board and Body of the Harmonization process. In each section you can find when and by which each the version is approved (e.g., “Approved by the VITALISE H2020 Living Labs' consensus report on XX/XX/XXXX”.)

The VITALISE Harmonization process is governed by two main groups, the VITALISE Harmonization Body and the VITALISE Harmonization Board. By VITALISE Harmonization Body we refer to a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to co-ordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and is consisted of representatives of each Living Lab in the consortium as well as independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

The aim of this Living Lab standard is to guide Living Lab operators and researchers to execute, develop and maintain a harmonized framework for systematic Living Lab practices. It is not a rigid and strict representation of what Living Labs are doing but it rather be used as guidelines towards the identification of common approaches. Living Labs are structures that encourage serendipity in the way that they are working and should be handled as such.

By Establishing Living Lab management system, the living labs will:

1. Promote the expansion and growth of Living Lab movement beyond current actors and customers,
2. Stimulate cross-organization and transnational research collaboration,
3. Enable data sharing and comparison of the research results,
4. Increase research quality, and
5. Define a common terminology and language among researchers and practitioners.

The Figure 8 defines the conceptual overview of the living lab management system presented in this standard document.

Figure 8: The key elements and conceptual overview of the living lab management system

The following key elements will concern the Living Lab community and will be further assessed in the next Standard Version.

1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) – terms and definitions: LLL introduces, lists and shortly defines a comprehensive catalogue of terms associated and included in different parts of the living lab standard (i.e. 2 to 9). The LLL is grounded on Wikipedia type of user interface, where definitions including overlapping terminology, will enable quick jumping between different descriptions and to in-depth descriptions in other standard sections. LLL will help to discuss living lab related issues among the different stakeholder, who currently are using varying terminology.

2. Living Lab Business Model (LLBM): “A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010) (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The purpose of the LLBM part is to identify different attributes associated with each nine BMC element. Having a unified way to describe LLBM enables quantitative business model comparison between different living labs as well as open ups possibilities to track changes in business model strategies.

3. Research process: The part ‘Living lab research process’ focuses on defining the key steps to execute and define a living lab research methodology. The part is comprised of (1) a common template to define research protocol, (2) ethical and data management plans, (3) participant recruitment procedures, (4) infrastructure selection procedure, (5) data collection procedures, (6) data analysis and comparison practices and (7) fair data practices for opening data. Each phase consists of aim, outcome and maturity level description. Furthermore, research process phases are interlinked with other living lab standard parts in order to identify which other items are relevant for each research process phase. Having a standard way to describe living lab research design helps developing a unified research methodology, which enables a robust results comparison across different studies, increasing the research quality.

4. Innovation process: Living Lab innovation process part focuses on defining in an unambiguous way, the different innovation management process phases which are or can be covered during the living lab data collection phase. This part defines an iterative and agile user-centered innovation and design process and align the phases with Technology Readiness Level (TRL) concept. TRL is widely adopted concept to describe developed solution maturity level. Respectively to research process, different innovation process phases are interlinked with other Living Lab standard parts in order to identify which of the other items are relevant for each process phase.

5. R&D services: R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its' customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities or parts of the Living Lab standard, needed to accomplish living lab R&D project as whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. In the long run, the aim is to define the Minimum Acceptable Service Level for each service type in order ensure service quality across the different Living Labs.

6. Living lab Research Infrastructure (RI): This part provides a classification schema and definitions for different types of Living Lab infrastructures. In regulation No 1291/2013, European Union Parliament and Council of the European Union (2013) defines RIs as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields”. The definitions and descriptions for (1) single-sited, (2) distributed, (3) virtual and (4) mobile living lab facilities are provided.

7. Data collection approaches. Data collection approaches consist of the following three sub-parts: (1) methods and tools, (2) devices and technologies and (3) validated questionnaires and instruments. This part provides a collection of practical data collection approaches, which can be combined in multiple variations when defining a living lab project research methodology.

7A Methods and tools part identifies and describes the different types of specific research methods, tools, and practices, which can be used for data collection during a living lab project. Among these are e.g. interviews, workshops and surveys. In the future, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular method in different living research contexts.

7B Devices and technologies defines a commonly used technological solutions to collect and analyse living lab research data. Correspondingly to 7A methods and devices, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular technology in a research setting.

7C. Validated questionnaires and instrument consists of a numerous scientifically validated surveys, scales, interventions or similar, known to be reliable measure-certain phenomenon. The Standard will especially promote questionnaires and instruments which are multilingual and freely available. If multiple instruments are available to measure same phenomenon, standard will make recommendation to make selections.

To conclude, it is important to clarify that the above-described conceptual overview and the included key elements of the living lab management system are preliminary concepts. Therefore, the names, details and concept itself can be changed in the following versions.

4.2 Scope of this document

This is the second draft version of the Health and Wellbeing Living Labs Standard (Version 0.2). The structure and content of this document will be continuously improved and a new version will be released every 6 months. The information presented are a result of an analysis performed in the VITALISE project and more details about the analysis can be found in the Deliverables of the project. The Parts that are not presented here are the ones that have not yet undergone a full circle of Harmonization. The rest of the document presents:

- **PART 1 Living Lab Lexicon (LLL):** collection of terms that are widely used in living lab performed activities

- **PART 2. Living lab business model:** The identified end users that can use the R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs
- **PART 5. R&D Services:** A list of R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs
- **PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure:** a first categorization of existing Living Lab infrastructures.
- **PART 7A. Methods and tools:** In this standard version identified methods and tools are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions
- **PART 7B. Devices and technologies:** In this standard version identified devices and technologies are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions

4.3 PART 1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)

VITALISE is creating a Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) with the aim of facilitating the use of terminology from Living Labs in the Health and Well-being sector. The LLL will be grounded on a Wikipedia type of user interface and will cover categories such as Strategy, governance & culture; Operations & infrastructure; Openness; Users & reality; Impact & value creation, and Stability of the living lab.

Table 12: Collected terms from LLs' activities

Collected terms from LLs' activities			
bottom up	european collaboration	integrative process	observation
co-design	experimentation	iterative feedback	open innovation ecosystem
community pilots	exploration	knowledge sharing	real life testing
constellation	feedback protection	lifecycle approach	regional collaboration
cross border living lab collaboration	governance	living lab methodology	small scale pilots
Cross-fertilization	human centered design	living lab methods and tools	stakeholders
demonstration (sessions)	human factor study	living lab research	user centered-design
end user involvement uptake inclusion	ideation	methodology	user design research
end users			

4.4 PART 2. Living Lab Business Model (LLBM)

“A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010) (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The living lab standard defines common attributes associated with each nine BMC element.

This standard version focuses on defining customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.

4.4.1 Customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs

End user: A person who ultimately uses or is intended to ultimately use the product, service or process. In living lab project, end user is defined as a primary study participant who voluntarily participates research after giving informed consent to be the subject of the research.

Living lab research infrastructure end user: A person or organization who purchases or uses living lab research infrastructure services to conduct a specific contract based research and development activity (often focusing on specifically defined end user group). Living lab research infrastructure end user can also be study participant (a.k.a. end user), if living project is focusing on developing living lab services and infrastructure.

End users can be classified to non-professional and professional groups. Typical non-professional and professional end-user groups in health and wellbeing includes the following:

- **Non-professional end users:**
 - **Consumers:** Those who buy goods or services for their own use.

- **Public health and social service clients:** Those who use public services.
- **Professional end users**
 - **Health professionals and managers:** A person providing health care treatment and advice based on formal training and experience. Also known as healthcare professional or healthcare worker.
 - **Social care workers and managers:** Those providing the practical support to help people cope with the day-to-day business of living based on formal training and experience.
 - **Policy and decisions makers:** Those responsible for making policies and decisions at local, regional, national or international level.

Business-to-Business Customer (B2B): B2B-customer is an organization that purchases living lab services from a living lab. B2B-customers can be classified to private, public, education/ research, civil society organizations and networks/cluster groups as follows:

- **Private sector organizations:** (business developers and researchers)
 - Tangible equipment and device manufactures
 - Health and social service providers
 - e-health, IT system and digital technology providers
 - Wellbeing and wellness service providers
 - Pharmaceutical companies
- **Public sector organizations:**
 - **Local level:** Municipals, cities and other local level public organizations providing e.g. health and social services such as primary health care.
 - **Regional level:** e.g. Regional hospitals providing secondary and tertiary care, councils, parliaments, and governments as well as other administrative organizations operating at regional level.
 - **National level:** Government agencies, departments or temporary pointed working groups responsible for the specific functions such as health and social services.
 - **International level:** European commission departments and agencies as well as other organizations operating at international and transnational level.
 - **Public funder:** Government or other European, national, regional or local public institutions who is providing public funding for a specific living lab living lab research project via call for application process.
- **Education and research organizations:**
 - **Higher education institutes:** Universities and Universities of Applied Sciences
 - **Other educational institutes** covering early childhood, primary, secondary and tertiary education
 - **Public research institutions/organizations** such as technical research centers and government laboratories.
 - **Private research organizations** such as technology and innovation centers
- **Civil society organizations:**
 - Non-governmental organizations (NGO) and nonprofit entities operating at international, national, regional or local level.
- **Networks and clusters:**
 - Company cluster organizations and company networks
 - International, national, regional and local networks

Typical approaches to define non-professional end users (a.k.a. study participants) in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 13.

Table 13: Classification approaches of non-professional end users commonly acting as a primary study participant in a health and wellbeing living lab research project.

Age or age group			
Specific age range			
Elderly	Adults	Youth	Children

Health status			
Healthy	Patient	Rehabilitant	Recovered/Survivor

A specific disease, disorder or disability			
ADHD	Dementia	Parkinsons' disease	Loneliness and Social Isolation
Autism	Down syndrome	Physical disability	Mental health
Cardiovascular disease	Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF)	Sleep apnea/apnea	Mild cognitive impairment
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)	Language disability	Substance abuse (drugs, alcohol)	Multiple sclerosis
Cognitive disorder (mild, major)	Intellectual disability/ Learning difficulty/ Mental retardation	Trauma patient (e.g., a spinal cord injury)	Neurodegenerative diseases

Clients of a specific service			
Child welfare	Nursing home	Employment service	
Early childhood education	Home care		

Vulnerable groups			
Minors/Children	Single parents with minor children	Persons subjected to psychological, physical or sexual violence	Substance users (drugs, alcohol)
Disabled people	Victims of trafficking in human beings	Ethnic minorities and immigrants	Isolated people
Elderly people	Persons with serious illnesses	Homeless people	Ex-prisoners and people with criminal background
Pregnant women	Persons with mental disorders		

Living lab research infrastructure end users and B2B-customers in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Researchers expertise

Researcher expertise	Brief use case description
Policy Makers	Studying the impact of new service models or new collaboration models in healthcare, designing or improving policies, gathering requirements for improving health and wellbeing of citizens, co-creation of research methodologies for policy making
Experts in communication studies	Defining written, oral, visual and digital communication within a certain workplace. Evaluating (multi professional) healthcare team collaboration, communication and debriefing in various healthcare situations in simulated environments (especially in Simulation lab)
Computer/Technology Scientists	Developing systems/tools/ technologies, testing and evaluating an ICT tool, prototype and real-life testing, computer vision & AI, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality, Cybersecurity
(Clinical, social, developmental, neuro-) Psychologists	Studying the behaviour and the mental wellbeing of participants, conducting psychometrics evaluation and real-life setting experimentation/observation/real life testing
Social workers/researchers	Investigating in accordance with the scientific methods and tools, studying the impact of new care models and/or care innovations on society, developing models for a caring and inclusive society
Researchers with clinical expertise	(Doctors, nurses, healthcare workers, specialists, physiotherapists etc.), conducting research of healthcare services and practices, research on symptomatology or epidemiology of a disease, analysis of clinical effects of research performed in the study, e.g; via real life testing
Experts in UX research and assessment	Developing the process for user experience design (UXD, UED, or XD) supporting user behavior through usability, usefulness, and desirability provided in the interaction with a product or service, addressing all aspects as perceived by users with a focus on the quality of the user experience. Studying and experimenting the best practices for UI/UX and evaluating user's experience in different situations and while using different tools
Experts in sport science	Experimenting novel training methods, and their effectiveness in various dimensions such as safety, engagement, and physical capabilities. Studying the impact of physical movements in various functions and wellbeing features
Experts in rehabilitation (physical, cognitive)	Physiology, physiotherapy, occupational health research, rehabilitation and prevention. Cognitive diseases

	assistive technology, neuromuscular rehabilitation assistive technology
Experts in performing arts	Creative health improvement (e.g. for cognitive decline) through music and dance (example: redesigning public spaces into healthy spaces: test and validate Smart methodologies, products and services through folk dance)
Business developers	Studying the product-market fit, matching a solution with a societal need, learning about the user acceptance of products and services, as well as about potential products to develop, willingness to pay, business model and ideal route to market
Pedagogues/educators	Evaluating different pedagogical approaches and their impact learning performance (especially in Simulation lab)
Experts in applied economics	Evaluating cost and performance in different healthcare processes, situations and public health
Experts in ergonomics and safety	Implementation and validation of ergonomic technologies/services to support workers and system performance, promoting ergonomics in working environments, improving both health/well-being and productivity, while avoiding occupational hazards
Citizen Scientists / users as co-researchers	User empowerment, training, design, analysis and implementation of strategies and methodologies for user engagement and for raising awareness and generating citizen participation
Biomedical researchers	Studying biochemical and physiological functions, investigating how the human body works with the aim of finding new ways to improve health. Biomedical engineering knowledge (Home hospitalization, Transitional Care, Multifunctional interaction), as well as digital biomarkers analysis (e.g., for cognitive state)
Experts in accessibility Design	Validating accessible Architectonics and escape route models with VR experiment and real-life simulations
Neuroscientists	Focusing on the brain and its impact on behaviour and cognitive functions (cognitive neuroscience, EEG-based BMI research, protocol / paradigm testing, study framework evaluation)
Innovation and design management researchers	Ecosystem and innovation management research, social network analysis. Evaluating how health and wellbeing ecosystem operates between different actors at local, regional, national and international level, including also scaling and commercialization
Experts in organizational studies	Co-creation, experimentation, organizational research, experts by experience / peer support included. Evaluation how multistakeholder collaboration and co-creation is done and how effective it is. Evaluates experimentations and experimentation culture. How users are involved into these processes

Data Scientists	Collecting, analysing and interpreting digital data, such as data analytics in healthcare and digital patient recordings (how patient information recording process is managed and utilized during the intervention by using digital tools in simulated situations)
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4.5 PART 5. R&D Services

R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities. R&D Services are parts of the Living Lab standard needed to accomplish a living lab R&D project as a whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. Living lab R&D services are classified into the following categories:

1. Networking and capacity building
2. Project planning and management
3. Market and competitor intelligence services
4. Co-creation
5. Testing and validation
6. Advisory services
7. Marketing and sales support

It is noted that some of the services can be included in multiple categories

Depending on the nature and the scope of each service, the structure and the elements of the descriptive information vary. Below, follows a brief explanation of the R&D services structure:

Section	Description
Description	In the description field it is given a general overview of the service (e.g., definition, scope, followed processes etc.)
R&D service categories	Here it is indicated the category (or categories) to which belongs the service
Key characteristics in living lab context	In this field are highlighted the most important points/aspects of the service in a Living Lab framework
Pre-tasks	By pre-tasks we mean the several steps that are considered important to be completed before the delivery of the service
Participants' role	Participants' role refers to the particular actions/activities that are expected to be achieved by the stakeholders during the service delivery
Objectives	In this part are identified the various goals that are envisaged to be accomplished during the delivery of the service
Methods	This field refers to the methodology that stakeholders could follow for the service implementation (e.g., focus groups, training sessions, workshops, seminars, presentations, interviews etc.)

Tools	By tools we mean the specific instruments which could be possibly exploited during the service (e.g., questionnaires, sensors, Teams meeting, Zoom, whiteboards etc.)
Process phase	Here it is indicated the phase or stage during which the service is usually delivered

4.5.1 Access to data

Description: Referring to service, which enables customers to access or retrieve data from one or more databases consisting of relevant data, based on mutual agreements respecting ethics and GDPR, which can be used for development or testing purposes.

R&D service categories: Market and competitor intelligence services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually 2 sources: already existing data, new data collected
- Data must be anonymized and encrypted
- Consent from participants have been previously acquired by the LLs when it's required by ethical and legal legislations
- Type of data: demographics/personal data, health-clinical data (e.g., cognitive, treatment changes, physical performance, care to rehabilitation), measure data, sensors' data (brain activity)
- For open data, FAIR data principles should be followed
- Ethical approval and GDPR processes when needed

Pre-tasks:

- Create a database to store data
- Define the accessibility of the database (public or limited access) and how data are collected (in an integrated way or occasional/ad hoc databases/infrastructures)
- It is, usually, needed a request that is passed to the responsible of databases

4.5.2 Intake and matching

Description: During this service, the customer's (e.g., a company, SME, a start-up, a researcher) development and testing needs are clarified for the project planning purposes. It also includes the process of mapping the customer's needs and co-designing of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project and Living Lab capabilities to offer the particular project.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Can be both open discussion or more focused
- Usually at the beginning of the research process
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- Duration varies-30 minutes (very short from) to few hours or days. In most of the cases there are multiple meetings taking place/more than one contact
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: Researchers, clinicians, customers, students

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Pre-tasks:

- Discuss and understand who the customers are and what their needs are.
- Agree to a plan -usually it is made a document/contract- (set goals, explore the different services, engage the operational team)
- Revise & follow-up activities with the customer

Objectives

- Make a project proposal/offer between the relevant stakeholders
- Make a project contract

Methods:

Client's needs elicitation methodology, interview/focus group/questionnaires for defining the project and collecting the needs, co-design of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project

4.5.3 Capacity building

Description: Training, knowledge sharing and awareness raising, site visits and event arrangement. Offering training for end-users and/or practitioners to improve their skills and knowledge about Living Lab approach, co-creation, iterative development and healthcare and wellbeing market. Stimulating knowledge sharing and awareness raising by publishing professional and scientific publications and arranging events, site visits and seminars.

R&D service category-ies: Networking and capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The way of knowledge sharing and transfer depends on the project and on the purpose
- Use of short-term or long-term methods and courses
- Material can be both created for a purpose but also some available online

Participants' role:

- Service beneficiaries become trainees
- Living Labs can offer support for the design and facilitation of capacity building programs

Methods: Co-creation methodology, focus groups, training sessions (tech & non-tech), ethical training & legal in large scale settings, seminars, presentations, workshops, webinars, forums, websites and web-engines, events, site visits, publications, summer schools, degree program, methodological training, how to use new product

4.5.4 Clinical trials

Description: Clinical trials are experiments or observations done to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of new solution by monitoring its effects on large groups of people. Subjects are typically divided into two or more groups, one having "real treatment" by using the developed solution and the other group(s) using tried-and-true solution or not using any solution. The results are compared between the groups to evaluate the impacts.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Clinical trials are similar to impact assessment and validation test activities but follow more strict validation and approval process.

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Objectives

- To find out if new solutions are safe and effective
- Get official approval for new solution

Methods:

- Has multiple phases and classes which depend on the developed solution

4.5.5 Co-creation session

Description: Co-creation session is a facilitated group activity to find solutions for a specific problem by gathering ideas, solutions and insights from workshop participants while using variety of methods. Depending on the workshop focus, it may comprise ideation, concept development and testing. Typical duration for short workshop is from 45 minutes to 90 minutes, medium-length workshop from 90 minutes to 3 hours, and long-workshop from 3 hours to 1 day. The number of participants may vary depending on how many facilitators are available, and what kind of working methods are utilized. Typically, a workshop facilitated by a single facilitator consists of six to eight persons. Number of participants are sometimes numbered to enable them to work in pairs.

R&D service category-ies: Co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Fundamental features: Requires (1) facilitator(s), (2) interaction/is interactive, (3) iterative process
- Can be applied in almost all phases: e.g., ideation, concept creation/testing, prototyping, prototype testing
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- It is a service but also a generic method
- Duration varies, but usually 2-3 hours
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: researchers, clinicians, students (e.g., paediatric project, project on language and communication). Depending on the concept all actors of the quadruple helix are contacted, number of users depends also on the stakeholders. Engagement of different stakeholders can also be achieved by running series of sessions

Participants' role:

- In the beginning of the innovation process, involve the users as the creators
- If there is a product with higher Technology Readiness Level (TRL), a ready Minimum Viable Product (MVP) is more like a focus group,
- Need finding session, focus group is more of an evaluation,

Pre-tasks: prepare session upfront with the sketches, if focus group - open questions (sent beforehand), workshop preparation template

Objectives (varies depending on researchers' interest):

- Co-creation session: Finding solutions for a specific problem with or without prototypes or mock-ups. Co-creating the actual design, sketch interfaces, make the solution tangible, Drafting (prototypes, drawing), mock-ups
- Demo-session: specifically, setup to explain about the use of a prototype or market ready product and gather (first) feedback. Often done before launching a test.
- Business model session (broader, a service?): developing and defining a business model (e.g., potential customers, sales channels, distributors, value chain, the Willingness to Pay, revenue streams etc.

Methods: Brainstorming, use simulations, group discussion / focus groups, semi-structured focus group, survey, questionnaire

Tools: Projection walls, visual mock-ups, use tangible tools for prototyping (e.g. wearables), team groups, polling (tech); questionnaires, focus groups, idea generation techniques, post-it notes, creative supplies, art supplies,

Online tools: Online system for idea generation, Teams meeting, Zoom with breakout rooms, Google meet, Miro whiteboard, Mural.co

4.5.6 Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking

Description: Quantitative and qualitative methods are used to evaluate the size of the market both, in volume and in value (also known as market studies). Customer segments, buying patterns, competition, and the economic environment are defined to identify the regulations and the barriers to entry. Defining the market by listing and describing current, future, direct and indirect competitors and analysing their competitive offering (e.g., SWOT) and user experience. Comparing offerings by measuring the performance of the developed products, services, or processes against those, which are considered to be the best in the industry. Can consist also of literature reviews to a search and evaluation of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area.

R&D service category-ies: Market and competitor intelligence services

Participants' role: Competitors or stakeholders interested in collaborations, can be done by students or experts.

Objectives:

- Identify the “space” for innovation, not analysing only specific segments, but also looking for new opportunities
- Analyse market acceptance, support scalability and transferability potential, focus can be domestic/international/global market,
- Identify direct and/or indirect competitors, qualitative or quantitative description of the market, focus can also be in research context or innovation management practices

Methods: Desk research, acquiring the information from the experts in the field, following the market as a job profile/duty, the people working know specific segments/areas, bibliometric studies, literature reviews to a search and evaluate of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area, technology exploitation, market analysis, benchmarking, other methods combined with interview(s) with a leading reference organisation or expert(s), assessment of technologies, knowledge syntheses (systematic and scoping reviews), evaluations methods of intervention (ETMI method), workshops and sessions, measures of satisfaction of users

Tools: SWOT analysis, business model canvas, Innovation management standard (CEN/TS 16555 - covered 7 standards, after ISO 56002:2019)

4.5.7 Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study

Description: Concept test is a low cost and quick process in which a high-level concept is tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews and surveys. In order to conduct a concept test, preliminary concept description must exist in written or visual format, which is then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback for the initial concept proposal and its possible variations. Concept test can also include a feasibility study, which also covers technical, economic, legal, operational and scheduling issues relating the proposed concept. In all, concept-testing phase verifies if a concept has market interest, while feasibility study shows if the product or service based on concept can be developed. Collected feedback also includes improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Core service in LL

Participants' role: Two main actors (projects and companies), joint work among Living Labs and interested partners/stakeholders

Process phase: After concept co-creation

Objectives:

- Verify if a concept has market or research interest,
- Testing early “prototypes” to get feedback for development, identify improvement suggestions,
- Concept feasibility test focuses on verifying if concept can be technically/economically done (preliminary assessment),
- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs, identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests, personalized in the client need and varies case by case

Methods: Survey, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz

Tools: Paper prototype, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), visual VR can be used to test-multitasking (real work), long term evaluations, interviews, questionnaires

4.5.8 Equipment and facility rental service

Description: Offering equipment, labs, spaces, human resources and other facilities for rent. Some Living Labs do this based on a win-to-win agreement where money does not change hand. Also, some Living Labs require research collaboration when renting.

R&D service category-ies: Networking and capacity building

Participants' role: In some cases, researchers can visit the LL and use the provided facilities free of charge

Objectives:

- Getting temporary human, space, technical or other facility resources,
- Enable research collaboration

Methods: Payment, research collaboration grounded on Living Lab resources

Tools: Simulation lab

4.5.9 Expert opinion, and advisory services

Description: Expert(s) who have long-standing practical and/or scientific experience in the field of enquiry provide(s) a well-founded written or oral answer for your questions, including the ethics domain/ ethics guidelines, and offer(s) advisory services on the use of specific equipment. Expert(s) are discussing ideas and problems from a different angle to respectfully challenge, test and refine ideas (e.g. as devil’s advocate looking for problems). Qualified and traceable arguments in favor of and against a specific position in an applied issue to support decision-making and development activities. Professional work is a paid service, but “consultation” can be a free of charge service. In most cases it is done by Living Lab on its own, hosting organization personnel, subcontractor.

R&D service category-ies: All categories

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Typically consists of one-to-one relationship between the customer and the expert, but may include opinions from multiple experts.
- Internal or external experts (local, national and international experts)
- Multidisciplinary collaboration/Pool of experts

Objectives:

- Offer advice on UX or usability studies,
- Consulting care solutions (ICT and devices), in specific/narrow fields in which Living Lab has experts (e.g., energy consumption calculations),
- Consulting on consent and ethics requirement and processes,
- Consulting technical solutions (ICT, medical and other devices, sensors, wearables, health apps, machine learning, medical engineering)
- Consulting legal issues, networking and contacting people (e.g., doctors, academia, pharmacy, healthcare professionals, policy makers, local ecosystem actors), research ideas,
- Innovation management, interventions,
- Creation of training materials and processes

Methods: One to one and group discussion, advisory board, expert identification

Tools/Online tools: ethical tools, training materials

4.5.10 Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)

Description: Foresighting is a practice of exploring expected and alternative futures. Trend is a general tendency or direction evident from past events increasing or decreasing in strength of frequency of observation. A weak signal is an indicator of a potentially emerging issue that may become significant in the future. “Wild card” is a high-impact event that seem too incredible or is considered too unlikely to happen; yet many do happen.

R&D service category-ies: Market and competitor intelligence services, Co-creation

Objectives:

- Policy consulting,
- Create a future vision,
- Identify new opportunities and risks,

Methods: Back casting, brainstorming, user/citizen panels, workshop/session, expert panel, interview, literature review, role playing, scenarios, survey, SWOT, wild card & weak signals, science fiction/crazy ideas

4.5.11 Temporary research funding

Description: Providing funding (or an investment) for research, product and business development for small and medium-sized companies or start-ups. Typically, funding is targeted for short-term small-scale experiments or if an externally funded project has resources for this kind of activity (e.g., open calls). Also, it can be done in collaboration with local research centers, publicly funded “development companies” and networks or similar.

R&D service category-ies: Networking and capacity building, project planning and management

Objectives:

- Providing funding to execute small scale Living Lab project (e.g. testing)

Methods: Offering funds within funded projects for small-scale testing or co-creation

4.5.12 Grant writing and funding application support service

Description: Offering tailored support by identifying the proper local, regional, national and international funding instruments, helping to write and manage a funding application process including finding the right partners for the project if needed. In most cases a Living Lab will become a project partner, but it can also be provided as a paid service without participation.

R&D service category-ies: Networking and capacity building

Objectives:

- Acquiring/providing funding for “customer” to execute a Living lab project or buy Living Lab services,
- Getting project partner for a Living Lab project

4.5.13 Idea selection and testing

Description: Idea testing is a low-cost and quick process in which high-level ideas are selected (i.e. ranked) or tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews, surveys or during the workshop. In order to conduct idea testing, different high-level ideas are pre-described in written or in visual format, and then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback on the already existing idea proposal. Feedback can also include improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Objectives:

- Collect feedback, prioritize ideas or different alternative options,
- Lowering development risk by selecting the best/most promising idea for further development,
- Challenge the ideas from different perspectives

Methods: Co-creation workshop, interviews, focus groups, surveys, questionnaires, small group discussions, informal talks

4.5.14 Impact assessment and validation test

Description: Impact assessment is a formal, evidence-based procedure that assesses the total outcome that comes as a result of the tested activity, above and beyond what would have happened anyway. Depending on the duration and scope of the validation process impact can be evaluated on individuals, organizations and the society in the short, medium and long term. Validation is the documented act of demonstration that a product or a service will consistently lead to the expected results. Validation test ensures that the product or the service actually meets the defined requirements and demonstrates that the solution fulfils its intended use when deployed on appropriate real environment.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The validation test is usually designed by LL
- Validation testing has to meet some minimum TRL level in order reliable test the solution impact

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will consistently lead to the expected results and meet defined requirement
- Evaluate social impact
- Quantify change after solution usage

Methods: Survey, observation, pre and post measurement (short and long term), quantitative measures (e.g., physiological measures), feasibility study, usability study, interviews

Tools/online tools: Questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors, thermal cameras

4.5.15 Innovation network orchestration

Description: Establishing productive working relationship between existing and previously unconnected but complementary actor parties and helping them (companies, public health and other sector, academia, and end-user stakeholders) to work together properly and well. Handling conflicts and supporting interactions.

R&D service category-ies: Networking and capacity building

Objectives:

- Establish new collaboration relationships,
- Promote Living Lab methodology and raising awareness,
- Lobbying Living Lab movement

Methods: Events, seminars, webinars, conferences, one-to-one meetings, site visits, publications (scientific and professional), memberships in local/regional/national/international associations/networks

4.5.16 Large-scale real-life testing and piloting

Description: Similar to small-scale testing but with a longer duration or larger number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group. During piloting, the aim is to evaluate the full scale and near or fully functional product(s) or service(s) at the system level in real environment with real end-users to make sure that the solution is scalable. Includes often impact assessment and validation testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually, the aim of the testing defines the number of participants
- Sometimes, for large numbers the LL can hire a specialized company for support

Objectives:

- Evaluate scalability,
- Evaluate system level impact and functionality,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, longitudinal study, sensors, interview, survey, observation, ethnographic studies, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

4.5.17 Legal, regulation and safety standard support

Description: Providing support to navigate to the legal, regulatory and safety standard requirements and help planning to meet the requirements.

R&D service category-ies: All categories

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Legal design and decision-making support
- Support on signed agreements, protocol
- In some cases, external contractors for IPR, RGDPD

Objectives:

- Similar to expert opinion and advisory services but focusing on legal and regulatory issues

4.5.18 Living Lab project planning and management

Description: Planning project goals, costs, schedule, list of deliverables, delivery dates and resources. Written project plan for one or multiple innovation stages is made. In the project management, planned tasks are completed by executing, monitoring, controlling, and closing the work of a project team to achieve specific goals and to meet specific success criteria at the specified time.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management

Objectives:

- Successful development and implementation of all project procedures,
- Supervision and quality control,
- Internal/external communication,
- Optimization of the allocated resources,
- Getting clients and funding,

Tools/Online tools: Project and planning management tools, Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Excel, email, phone, messaging application

4.5.19 Marketing and sales support

Description: Providing marketing and sales support for 1) making right contacts by giving business contacts, sales and business leads, 2) setting up and arranging meetings and events, 3) showcasing products and services in a showroom or giving online/onsite visibility in Living Lab own communication channels, 4) providing “user approved” certification, and 5) offering soft landing support to help to set up business in given Living Lab country or region.

R&D service category-ies: Marketing and sales support, networking and capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- It can be introductory to healthcare companies and service providers and goes up to the point of developing a BM

Objectives:

- Finding right contacts and customers for Living Lab clients,

Tools: “user approved” certification, showroom, showcasing, business meetings, interviews, events, soft landing services, sales/business leads

4.5.20 Panel management

Description: Panel is a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g. patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Panel members have given their contact details and other profiling information, which enables fast recruitment for specific research activities as they come up.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management, networking and capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Group of patients, students but also experts, experts by experience and other staff can be used as a panel (agreement is necessary in every case)
- Having engagement procedures in place (win to win situation), social activities

Objectives:

- Enable fast participant recruitment,
- Lower the management effort (no need to fill profile information multiple times)

Method: survey, recruitment collaboration with medical professionals (e.g., in hospital ward)

Tools/Online tools: intake questionnaire, phone, open calls in social media/web, posters, email, personal invitations

4.5.21 Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing

Description: Post-market surveillance is a “real world” test of medical innovations in patient subgroups. It is a practice of monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market. Market acceptance testing focuses on collecting market feedback for the next revision development and tracking the solution performance in real competitive market conditions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation, Market and competitor intelligence services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually within a clinical or community research context (within the context of specific projects/the products that come out as research outcomes) and not as a standalone service.
- As normal customer feedback collection and health promotion, for continuum improvement of the tool

Objectives:

- Monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market,
- Evaluate social impact,
- Identify new opportunities for business and research

Methods: Survey, observation, interviews, helpdesk logs, technical logs, complain reports, pre and post measurement (long term), market studies

Tools/online tools: questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors

4.5.22 Prototyping test

Description: Prototyping test is a low cost and quick process in which a product or service with limited functionality and interaction is tested with real end-users. An interactive prototype product or service must be available so real end-users or experts can experience it. This prototype test can be, for instance, an interactive mock-up of a web service, which interface looks like a real thing. One can navigate through different screens and see simulated content. Also, the service prototype can consist of role-playing exercise to simulate service encounters. The main aim is to collect feedback on a 'close to real' user experience as possible, but at a lower cost. Different methods such as interviews, surveys and observations can be used.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- From rapid prototyping to the MVP
- IT solutions/Physical and cognitive exercises

Objectives:

- Similar to proof-of-concept but testing higher fidelity solution,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- Provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Survey, observation, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz, usability tests, role playing

Tools: Paper prototype, wireframes, interactive mockups, scaled down prototypes, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), video recording, usability questionnaires, eye tracking

4.5.23 Public procurement support services

Description: Public procurement (e.g., related to research activities) is governed by EU and national rules. Support with public contract issues and the public procurement process is given to help clients to meet the tendering criteria and/or join the tendering process. Also helping public authorities to establish market dialogue when developing the public procurement announcement. This includes Pre-Commercial Procurement and innovative procurement processes.

R&D service category-ies: Networking and capacity building, co-creation, advisory services, marketing and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Pre-commercial procurement, innovative procurement, public procurement
- Project based
- Validation Software (integration) - Hardware (operational validation in real environment)
- Legal design and decision-making support

Methods: Planning process based on co-creation, pre-commercial procurement (PCP), innovative procurement

4.5.24 Simulation test

Description: Simulation is a technique that creates a situation and environment, which allows end-users to experience a representation of a real event in a risk-free environment. A predefined simulation scenario defines a particular set of conditions to resemble authentic situations in a location where a simulation experience takes place to test and to gain understanding of tested solution and related human interactions. After simulation event, facilitators and end-users re-examine the simulation experience, and various aspects of the completed simulation are discussed.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Mainly for ICT solutions
- Simulation labs, smart home that simulate real-life home/specific scenarios to simulate real space

Objectives:

- Simulate real-life situations and behavior but lower cost,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Simulation test, virtual reality (VR), usage scenarios, interview, debriefing, observation, survey, Wizard of Oz, sensors, usage logs, hospital ward, interactive patient mannequin, usage scenarios,

Tools: Audio recording, video recording

4.5.25 Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation

Description: A small-scale real-life experiment is a small-scale and short-term preliminary study conducted to evaluate feasibility of the suggested product or service and to improve it based on the testing result. Testing includes a small number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Usually lab-based studies
- Can mostly involve qualitative feedback
- Testing quality and user satisfaction,

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will work also in real-life setting,
- Evaluate usability before engaging more people in testing,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, survey, interview, survey, observation, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

Tools: Validated questionnaires, sensors

4.5.26 Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping

Description: Identifying groups, organizations, and people who are relevant stakeholders. Prioritizing and ranking stakeholders based on their perspectives and interest. Mapping the relationship between different stakeholders and company objectives. Deliverable(s) Written report.

R&D service category-ies: Networking and capacity building, Market and competitor intelligence services, co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Within a research context / for programs and projects.
- Trying to promote a diversity-centered design

Pre-tasks: Searching and listing all the interested stakeholders/partners, contacting them, and then mapping possible contributors

Objectives:

- Identifying relevant/key/negative stakeholders,
- Identify stakeholders' interest,
- Provide information to participant recruitment

Methods: Focus group, workshop, interviews, questionnaires methodology, social network analysis, two-dimensional matrix (e.g., power, influence, interest/need, support/attitude), primary/secondary/tertiary stakeholder, the salience model

Tools: Online whiteboard (e.g., Miro), stakeholder mapping template

4.5.27 Usability testing

Description: Usability testing is a technique used to evaluate a product by testing it in order to give direct input on how real users use or would use the product or service. Usability inspection is conducted when a professional evaluator inspects a user interface and gives an expert opinion regarding the usability. This approach does not involve real user. Usability testing with real users includes real users who have no prior exposure to the product or service. In the context of Living Labs is mostly provided real user testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Objectives: Identify usability problems, provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,

Methods: Moderated/unmoderated, remote/in-person, comparative testing, open ended explorative testing, user satisfaction, phone/video interview, usability lab testing, session recordings, observation

Tools: SUS, QUEST, feasibility assessment and other several tests, eye-tracking camera

4.6 PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure

In regulation 1291/2013, the EU Parliament and Council of the EU define Research Infrastructure (RI) as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields” [1]. Living lab RIs consist

- **Single-sited facility:** Unified single body of equipment at one physical location
 - Laboratory or smart home
- **Distributed facility:** Facilities, resources and services that are geographically scattered in multiple location
 - City, city district, outdoor space (e.g. nature/hiking trails)
 - sensor networks, network of homes
- **Virtual access-based facility:** Resources and services that are exclusively available via online internet based tools.
 - Access and ability storage scientific data and repositories, tools for virtual collaboration, various computer services,
- **Mobile facility:** Facilities and resources which can be easily moved to from one place to another
 - Handheld devices and non-handheld equipment

4.7 PART 7B. Devices and technologies

This Part presents a taxonomy for identifying and classifying the data that are collected in Living Lab environments and consequently link the devices that are used for collecting each data category. The aim of the taxonomy is to help finding the appropriate digital data collection tools for living lab research and/or expand understanding about available tools and their possibilities. Furthermore, the taxonomy aims to facilitate data collection by driving a unified representation schema of the collected datasets enabling the the cross-organizational collaboration and the accessibility of Living Labs to external stakeholders.

Table 15: Devices and technologies provided by Living Labs

			Definition
Categories of devices for data monitoring and collection	Environmental monitoring		characterize and monitor the environment, establish environmental parameters and conditions. As environment we refer to the person's surroundings either indoors or outdoors.
	Human monitoring	Biometrics	biological measurements — or physical characteristics — that can be used to identify individuals and their unique characteristics such as fingerprint scanning or voice recognition
		Biosignals and physiological monitoring	physiological and physical measures of the human body's functions, in individuals. This can occur in a resting condition or in response to certain bodily or environmental conditions. It includes also fitness related metrics

		(Primary) Vital signs	a group of the six most important medical signs that indicate the status of the body's vital function (diastolic/systolic blood pressure, body temperature, heart rate, respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, body height, body weight, BMI, head circumference)
		Cognitive ability and mental processes	Measuring the processes involved in the acquisition of knowledge, reasoning and management of information and the brain-based skills we need to carry out any task
		Activity and behavioral monitoring	monitoring the individuals' physical activities and tracking their performance. Monitoring behavior and activities of daily living (ADLs)
Categories of technologies for interventions	Assistive Technology		technologies used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of individuals, the feeling of autonomy, safety and general wellbeing or also supporting participation.
	Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)		allows for a two-way flow of information through an interface between the user and the technology through a simulated experience that can be similar to or completely different from the real world
	Mobile and Computer Games		all the digital games that are used as interventions for health and wellbeing not including XR

Category	Subcategory
Environment monitoring	Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)
	Technical alerts (Flood)
	Technical alerts (Smoke)
	Environmental Temperature (air or water temperature)
	Luminosity
	Indoor movements
Biometrics	Face recognition
	Voice recognition
	Physiological and behavioural biomarkers

Biosignals and physiological monitoring (excluding vital signs)	Electrophysiological timeseries
	EEG
	ECG
	EMG (electromyography)
	GSR (galvanic skin response)
	Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)
	Blood oxygen
	Blood sugar level
(Primary) Vital signs	Diastolic blood pressure
	Systolic blood pressure
	Heart rate
	Body temperature
	Respiratory rate
	Oxygen saturation
	Body height
	Body length
	Body weight
	Body Mass Index
Cognitive ability and mental processes	Questionnaires of cognitive function
	Cognitive tasks and paradigms
	Memory
	Attention
Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	Body position
	Orientation
	Walking speed
	Gait
	Human balance
	Inverse kinematics data
	Movement measurement
	Physical activity
	Physical performance
	Sleep
	Steps
	Stress level
	Physical performance
	Digital questionnaires and surveys

	Video stream
	Fall detection
	Gesture detection
	Audio stream
Assistive Technology	Cognitive training
	Supporting bathroom usage
	Walk assistance
	Mobile apps
	Alarm system
	Natural language understanding
Virtual reality/interactive technology	Alternative and augmentative Interaction
	Intuitive user interface
Mobile and Computer Games	Mobile games
	Computer games

5 Conclusion

This document presents information about the collection of data and analysis towards the creation of the Standard Version 0.2 for Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain. Although the name of this deliverable is Standard version 2, the authors decided to name the Standard v0.2 as not all the parts have undergone Harmonization process yet. From the work that has been done so far, the authors concluded that there are various domains that will be benefited from the Harmonization processes and that there is need for Harmonization in various contexts (Section 4.1). The Standard Version 0.2 is an improved and updated version of 0.1 but still missing information for specific sections. The attempt will continue in an iterative way and its results will be released every 6 months. VITALISE consortium envisions to create a methodology that will continue to evolve even after the end of the project and that will be adopted by other thematic areas Living Labs (e.g., urban Living Labs) to capture the particularities of each domain and to identify the similarities across Living Lab practices.

6 References

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1

<p>Open Call- harmonization board & body in VITALISE website</p>	<p>Open Call- harmonization board ENoLL MailChimp</p>
<p>Apply for the VITALISE Harmonisation Board and Body!</p> <hr/> <p>VITALISE project invites all Living Lab and Harmonisation experts and any individual interested in the Living Lab offerings and methodologies to join the Harmonisation Board and Harmonisation Body and help in the process of defining the next Standards Version for Health and Wellbeing Living Labs!As...</p> <p>🕒 NOVEMBER 18, 2021 </p> <p>READ MORE ></p>	<p>Dear Member,</p> <p>Today is the final day to sign your interest to join the Harmonization Board for Living Labs.</p> <p>The challenge. In recent years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures that enable research studies in real life environments with the involvement of multiple stakeholders. Due to lack of a harmonization framework many project-oriented Living Labs that serve specific research purposes and have a lifecycle similar to a projects' duration have emerged, leading to higher costs, non-optimal use of time and resources and limited exploitation of research results from local communities. At the same time Living Labs need sustainable business models to offer their valuable services in the Research and Development community.</p> <p>The solution. It is time to address these challenges and bring all Living Labs together through our Harmonization Body to promote Open Research and Innovation.</p> <p>The Harmonization Board. This Board will be composed of representatives of Health and Wellbeing Living Labs from the VITALISE consortium as well as external people with expertise and interest in Living Lab offerings but also in Harmonization procedures. This</p>